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tjyft v&ajypum; rsm; wó f ajymol ⁴ Esh em; axmi íol ⁵ [lí tenf, qí vEíDí vlt yígon/ talumi ít &mwvpcí tjzpf tysuíwpcí Esh ywíouí jzppóíwpcí vnf; vlt yígon/ ívlt ycsuíoní [ajymp&m] [lí jzpfímygrn/ ajymp&mwvpcí &í som pum; ulí tjyft v&ajymjzplurn [jzpygon/ xí [ajymp&m] oní teuft "yíh, íulí qílvoní [k rsvíom; ztygon/ ⁶ teuft "yíh, bnf ajymo Esh íemol um; &í tuírt a0; Esh tqúft pyíulíwní tajymi ítví jzplí; wwíygon/ ítcííulí atmuázmfyyg tjyft v&ajypum; rsm; jzi híwi fygrn/

tjyft v&ajypum; (1)

(u) at;? tqí íajvm;/

(c) [kvíulí ajyygw, í ' gayrh...

(*) bm? ' gayrvnf ajymyg/ yó íyó híví, ví íajymyg/ bmr ítm; emp&mr vlygbt;/

(C) t ílválumi íyg/ odv, í [kvívm;/

azmfyyg tjyft v&ajypum; wó f (u) oní ajymo jzpygon/ (c) oní em; axmi íol (emol) jzpygon/ (u) Esh (c) wí \ tjyft v&ajypum; oní olví EíDí om odv; jybáom tajctae wpcí jzpyíwpcí jzpygon/ ywDef, usi &í tjcm; olísm; (wwí v) ⁷ em; vnbí &í urní [kvíyg/ oláomí olváajymqíeáom talumi ít &mwvpcí tjzpf tysuí wpcí oní tpóajyjcí ír &í lumi í? jybáom ítmí írí Eí ící í r &í lumi í &yí í Eí ygon/ (u) oní tajctae wpcí (toulí &mxí? t &íft 0g) jrí í jzplí lumi í Esh (c) oní (u) avmuf íajctae jrí íol [kválumi í xéí, xéí, oní, oní Esh ajymqíeáolumi í olví ygon/

xílválumi hí tjyft v&ajypum; wó f quobí írlum; cñpíntí jzpláom bmompum; wpcíulí toíjyKí tcsi fcsi fajymqbuqfí í oabmjzploní [k qítsí ygon/

¹ xéí írí í ol/

² spoken language

³ written language

⁴ speaker

⁵ hearer/ listener

⁶ círí í armí ("Ejz) ? 2016/

⁷ third person

ajymoES lemolw\ajymqbuqfht & ywDef usi u x bE\$D\ tqiES h tajctaeu
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rs;u\ em;axmi \unjcif;tm;jzi h ajymo? emolw\ p\w&eoabmxm;ES h tajctae
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tjeft v&ajympum;(1)

- (u) aemfaemfv\
- (c) tifyg tif;..... tif
- (*) wu, ðemf
- (c) b, fwe\unmz;v\w\ at;.... at;.../
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tjeft v&ajympum;(2)

- (u) raelub, f\w\
- (c) rle\ [i f;cg;auR,w, /
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- (c) b, fol]] *si f;}} xnbñ;v\rob;f/
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- tpma\w, ? tn\ðawmi ðysnu&o;w, /
- (c) bmv?]]rs;}} of; jyðemf/
- (u) bm]]rs;}}v\w\
- (c) awm&awm\]]E\ f;}} avmu&w, /

¹ analysis
² omv&f 2003? 31/

t x u b a z m f y y g t j y e f t v e b a j y m p u m ; r s m ; w o f A e f p u m ; r s m ; u h a w d & y g o n / (u)
 a j y m o E S (c) e m o w l o n f t a j c t a e r w a l u m i f a w d & y g o n / (u) o n (c) \ a j y m p u m ; u h
 e m ; v n b a b m a y g u j c i f t m ; e n f a e o n f u l l o w k m ; r e h l y g o n / p o l z p & j c i f r n (c) \
 a j y m p u m ; r s m ; w o f a c w o l p u m ; ? A e f p u m ; ¹ r s m ; y g o i b a e o m a l u m i h j z p l y g o n / j r e l [i f c g ;
 a u r w , } ?] * s i f x n b o r ; w , } ?] r s m ; o b r ; j y }] E h f a v m u f & w , } [b o m A e f p u m ; r s m ; \
 t o h t e e f ² E S h t e u f t " y h , f u l l o h e e f a j y m q e h j c i f t a v h t u s i & t s o m t x u b a z m f y y g
 t a j c t a e w p t u h (u) E S h (c) w l u o m p u m ; p o f u h q u v u b o r ; E h f r n j z p l y g o n /
 x h a l l u m i h (u) a j y m o E S (c) e m o E s p o \ t a w o t t u h t a j c t a e u b j c m ; c s u a l u m i h
 p u m ; p o f o n f z h z h w l w u j c i f r & l u m i f ? j y w f a v m u f o b r ; E h b a l u m i f a w d r i e h l y g o n /

t j y e f t v e b a j y m p u m ; (3)

- (u) u d w l d , & w m ; /
- (c) & w , / a y y g o r f a & m ? a y y g w t a & m y /
- (u) y l w t t v n h q h
- (c) a t ; a v / t h l y a t t a l u m i f a r ; r , b x i w , /
- (u) [k w f v m ; / i g l r f n v u t s m ³ r & b o t / i f n ; O b /
- (c) i g l r f n v n f r & b o t /
- (u) o b r ; j y } a u m a w m h r s y /
- (c) [m - & j y d & j y }] x m ; a & n } e m ; o b r ; x h r , /

a z m f y y g o m " u w o f (u) E S f (c) o n f w u o l l y w o e f u s i f w p t r s a u s m i f o m ; ?
 a u s m i f o r s m ; t j y e f t v e b a j y m q h v e b y m u h p w l u t j z i h y h z m x m ; j c i f j z p l y g o n / p u m ;
 p o f w o f] u d w l d , } ⁴ ?] a y y g o r f } ⁵ ?] a y y g w t } ⁶ ?] y l w t } ⁷ ?] t h l y a t } ⁸ w l o n f p
 y w o e f u s i E S & i f e b j y d o t a w o t t u h b r s m ; o m e m ; v n e h l y g o n / x h a l l u m i h t j y e f
 t v e b a j y m p u m ; r s m ; o n f t u e l t o w t a e t x m ; w p t & o n f [k o a b m a y g u l y g o n /
 b o E S h t o u a r g o r f a u s m i f t a j c t a e u h t u c w e h l y g o n /

t j y e f t v e b a j y m p u m ; (4) - b m o m p u m ; \ v l y f i e f w m o e f

- | | | |
|-----------|--|-------------------|
| y b (1) | (u) q & m r u a e m u f u s v h r o i & b o t ; w h
(c) t h g q h r a j z & b t a y g h | today ; w m o e f |
| y b (2) | (u) a , m i f r a & - n a e t m ; v m ; /
(c) n n f u b m v l r v l v / a p s o b r ; r v m ; v h | today ; w m o e f |

¹ slang
² usage
³ lecture
⁴ tutorial
⁵ paper one
⁶ paper two
⁷ professor
⁸ international phonetic alphabet
⁹ functions of language

wpDDES fwpD) quibG &mwD fajmoblR [kvf a&;o! emoblR [kvzwo!
 quibG h&;vrfalLumi? talLumi,t&m? bmompum; [aom tcsur&sm;oni quibG fl
 qll&m tajcchtcsur&sm;jzpbni/ ptc&ur&sm;ul&wnfi bmompum;\ tv&ylwmOef
 r&sm;ul ptpri&Lunh&vi bmompum;w&vi (1) today;wmOef¹ (2) azmfyr&wmOef²
 (3) vrfn&ri&wmOef³ (4) tv&zelw&ri&wmOef⁴ [li to&ly&ly&sm; u&lym;on&ul aw&lyg
 on/ ⁵ ptc&ul& atmu&azmfy&yg E&li f&j&m;bmompum;r&sm;? w&li f&i&fom;bmompum;
 r&sm;j&zi&hom" u&ji p&pp&wi&fy&x&m;y&gon/

- y&pb(3) (u) Care your step! | today;wmOef
 (c) What?
 (u) Care your step! It's raining.
 (c) Thank you
- y&pb(4) (u) enpitsuwotsukatteremo ii desuka | t&m;emaey&ly | azmfyri
 (c) watashi no janaidesuga, chotto | i&si;v&ri&jzpy&ly | wmOef
- y&pb(5) (u) Sodesune | ne, yo → to&E&n&ly&D
 (c) Sodesuyo | → o&ri&ar&ly&ES& fit&r&st&om;tr&sm;q&ll
 o&ll&E&ef&ly&ll
 → 'yo' on&ri&rt&ku&ll&D&ji&ri&f&or&sm;ul
 aj&ym&q&ll&ci&f& r&ly&ly&yg/ 1/2&ll f&on&f[k
 q&ll&u ow&ri&sv&ll&ly&gon/
- y&pb(6) (u) te&an&m(i&D) [m&ll&ri&telum?
 (c) te&an&m(i&D) [m q, f, ll
- y&pb(7) (u) -a0; - c&ll& h&armi f&x&ef&vm;z&ll&w&vi f,*e&e&er&mz&m;z&ll&vm;*w&ar/
 (c) -vm; b&vi f&a0;Zmu&ll&vm;uw&z&ll&v&ll
 (u) aj&rmu&D&D&ul&vm; *w&ri
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 q&ll&fu, e&ll&vm; uw&z&ll&vm;
 (u) q&ll&fu, e&ll&vm; uw&ara0; v&rf&rm&v&n&f em;v&ll&t&qi&h&ya& ...

¹ informational function
² expression function
³ directive Function
⁴ dhatic function
⁵ c&ri&ri&? armi ("E&j&Z&)? 2016? 41-42/

tjyehajypum; yb(1) (2) (3)onf bmompum; \ wmoefsm;rs today;wmoefu
 azmfefvsu&ygon/ yb(1)onf twefpnfuricsufsm;rs wptsufzplygon/ yb(2)
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 Mum;a, mi Etonf[kqltsilygon/

¹ dislect
² gender
³ male
⁴ female
⁵ linking word

olrfrwf

olwtqkw? xm;crjybnh
 Aki kvwLurfn? armi hajmufusm;u
 &om;&no? ar;Mujlonf
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&S jlltr, f

Side by side (2) P-117

Arthur : Hi, Gloria, This is Arthur.

Can I come over and visit this evening?

Gloria : No, Arthur. I'm afraid I won't be home this evening. I'll be shopping at the supermarket.

Arthur : Oh. Can I come over and visit tomorrow evening?

Gloria : No, Arthur. I'm afraid I won't be home tomorrow evening. I'll be working late at the office.

Arthur : I see can I come over and visit this weekend?

Gloria : No, Arthur. I'll be visiting my sister in New York.

Arthur : Oh. Well, can I come over and visit next Wednesday?

Gloria : No, Arthur. I'll be visiting my uncle in the hospital.

Arthur : How about sometime next spring?

Gloria : No, Arthur. I'll be getting merried next spring.

Arthur : Oh!!

Gloria : Good- bye.

Arthur ES h Gloria t jyeft v e f ajmpum; u l l p p p j c i f

- Arthur u v m v n t c l u l z a u m i f a u m i f e s h a w m i f q l b o r ; w m u l l a w & y g r n /

- Gloria u t a l u m i f t r s t r s j y j d j i i f q l b o r ; w m u l l u m ; & y g r n /

- 1/2 1/2 t v n l m c l a w m i f j c i f r [k w a l u m i f t q l r s a w & y g o n /

- t n b r e s f t w l p o v l ' m w l u s o b r ; a o m Arthur \ p o v l c p m ; r l u l l o h ! ! t m a r # d w l o e s f t w l j r i a , m i f l u m ; a , m i e l l y g o n /

- t c e l a w l w j z n f j z n f a & a & o b o r ; y l z i h u t [r l u l y m y : a p o n /

- Gloria r e f r y s t a v ; & l l y g ; e y r l u l v n f a w l & y g r n /

- ' D t j y e f t v e f a j m p u m ; & l t q l r s j y l p & m i z p a p c l o n /

Steven J. Molinsky, Bill Bliss, 2011, Third edition.

jcih bhoysuf

tjyftv&ajmpum; rsm; ull avlvnjci f tm; jzi h pum; \aemu uG lwGf azmfyxm; jci f r&om teuft"y th, rsm; rsm; p&e oniu h w& ygon/ ajymo? emo E&D&om em; vn&om tajctaersm;? jzp&yf rsm; ulbm ow&xm; rE h ygon/ x bE&D& \ tjyft v&ajmpum; rsm; ull ywDef; usi fu r r w& taw& t M&ES h tm/ 2&uray: r&om rlvnfi avlvmo h oyt& & ygrn/ x h& M&umi h vpD&ES h vpD& em; vnE h ri u h [E h jci f jzp&on f [k o h oyt& si ygon/ ajymo? emobnf ywDef; usi ft aet xm; ES h taw& t M&ay: rlvnfi pum; pO& z& z& w& w& u v m jci f? pum; pO& o& z& n f o h; jci f? pum; pO& y s u b o h; jci f rsm; jzp& v m E h f on f [k jri ygon/ x h& M&umi h tjyftv& ajmpum; rsm; \ tmebi ES h y& d m, fu l em; vn&xm; jci f tm; jzi h wpD&ES h vpD& M&um; & b p& v& t& p m; r r sm; ul q i jci f o h oyt& y j y& ajyavsmh v m E h r n f [k q l t s i ygon/

edh

tjyftv&ajmpum; rsm; ull rlvnfi b m o m p u m; r s m; u l l x e f o r t x m; E h j c i f t m; j z i h] b m o m p u m; o n f a j y m i f v b n } [h o m o a b m u l v u f c h M u n i v m r n / b m o m p u m; w h f \ w e l z u l e m; v n f o a b m a y g u a p y g r n f [k , M u n i y g o n / E p a , m u E s f t x u f t j y f t v & a j m p u m; r s m; u l l p p b a v l v m j c i f ? t u e l t o w x m; j y d t j y f t v & a j m l u & a o m p u m; r s m; u l l p p b a v l v m j c i f p o n h a v l v m w i j y c i f o a w o e p m w r f r s m; u l l q u i v u f y l p a e y g a l l u m i f w i j y t y y g o n /

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po&woepmwr f ull Bago University Research Journal w&f xn& b o f x k v a O c d l a y; y g a o m y b t w u i o l v \ y g a r m u e s y f a ' g u l v m a t ; a t ; x e f ? v l t y b n f r s m; u l l j z n i p l u f t M u h y; y g a o m ' k v d y g a r m u e s y f a ' g u l v m & i & i b e f E S h j r e f m p m y g a r m u © (X m e r s ;) a ' g u l v m c i t i b e f u l t x t y i f a u s Z i w i w i g a l l u m i f r s v i w r f w i l a z n f y t y y g o n /

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ciri? armi f ("Ejzl)/ (2009)/ **bmomtjripmaytjri f** &e l u e l y k p m t l y w l u l /
 ciri? armi f ("Ejzl)/ (2016)/ (' k v d t l u t) ? **t w a A ' e d g e f** / & e l u e l The Key Collection/
 ri f o D P / (1997)/ **ri f o D P U A s m y g i f c y f** & e l u e l t o l l f t O l l f p m a y /
 x e f j r i l O D / (2007)/ b m o m a A ' o ' a A ' (v w v d t l u t) / & e l u e l /
 a t m i j r i D D ? a ' g u l v m / (2010)/ **b m o m p u m o h w o e /** & e l u e l y n m w e a q m i y E s w l u l /

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Side by Side (Book-2), Cambridge University.

Steven J. Molinsky, Bill Bliss, 2011, Third edition.

aw&qr; jrefjci f

O&E h i v i f ? (a u s m i f t l y l u d) ? t v i f o p a b m f g a q m i ? w u i o l v D i l y w e f ? i y e l v r f ? 1 / 2 a j r m u & y i u l u ? p p a w f r l l /

a' : v s w i f (u x l u) ? j r e f m p m x m e ? p p a w f w u i o l l v /

a' : p p l o m (u x l u) ? j r e f m p m x m e ? p p a w f w u i o l l v /